

REPORT:

*A1.2.2: Selection of Methods
(Experiments and Simulations) and
Microfluidic Devices for Characterising
Pressure Drop and Flow Resistance in
Newtonian and Particle-Laden Flows.*

Work package 1

2026-03-19

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A1.2.2 of the EPM Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2025, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

A1.2.2 M9	Using input from A1.2.1 and the technical report produced, RISE with support of FOG, IPQ, UofG, DTI, CMI, INESC MN, LEI, CETIAT and INRIM will select methods (i.e., experiment and simulation) to characterise pressure drop and flow resistance, considering different temperatures and different liquids. The selection will also include which microfluidic devices (e.g., commercial chips or transfer standard chips from EMPIR 20NRM02 MFMET) to characterise, and explorative methods for the possibility of measuring pressure drop and flow resistance for particle-laden flows. This report provides information to A4.3.3 and be shared to end-users and stakeholders.	RISE , FOG, IPQ, UofG, DTI, CMI, NESC MN, LEI, CETIAT, INRIM
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Funded by European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project (24NRM03 MFMET II) has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

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1 Scope

This report describes the selection of experimental and simulation-based methods for characterising pressure drop and flow resistance in microfluidic systems. Based on the results generated in activity A1.2.1 and the associated technical report, suitable approaches for measurements over a specific temperature range and with different fluids will be evaluated and identified.

The scope of this study includes the determination of the microfluidic devices to be characterised, including commercially available microfluidic chips and transfer standard chips developed as part of the EMPIR project 20NRM02 MFMET I. In addition, this report will investigate possible methods for evaluating pressure drop and flow resistance in particle-laden flows, where measurements may require adapted or novel techniques because of the challenges involved.

The results of this work will directly feed into activity A4.3.3 (interlaboratory comparison) and will be made available to end users and stakeholders to guide future metrological and application-oriented developments in the characterisation of microfluidic flows.

2 Microfluidic devices

To characterise pressure drop and flow resistance, the focus has been on microfluidic chips with different materials (**mainly glass and plastic**), different channel geometries, and/or channel architectures. The microfluidic plastic chips mainly have mini Luer connections, which are commonly used in microfluidics, or ‘through-hole’ as the interface type. The microfluidic glass chips, on the other hand, will be mounted or simply inserted in a chip holder (see **Figure 1**). This chip holder provides a reliable and leak-free connection interface. The chip can be easily replaced, and the holder can be reused. The chip holder is compatible with any 1/16” OD tubing.

Figure 1 - Glass chip (clamping) interface, manufactured by Micronit

2.1 Transfer standard microfluidic chips developed as part of MFMET I

In the previous EMPIR project, 20NRM02 MFMET I, glass and plastic microfluidic chips were exclusively designed and produced. These MFMET I chips are described further in a related report on Zenodo [[Link](#)]. The microfluidic glass chips from IMTAG and microfluidic plastic chips manufactured by microfluidic ChipShop, remaining from that project, will also be used in the 24NRM03 MFMET2 project.

2.1.1 Microfluidic glass chips

The so-called MFMET I Glass Transfer Standards Chips (short: MFMET I glass), manufactured by IMTAG, originally comprise eight different designs, of which the first seven designs (see **Figure 2**) each have a channel with the same geometric dimensions (width 1000 μm , depth 50 μm , length 40 mm). This channel (channel 1 on each of the seven microfluidic chips) is to be used for further experiments.

Figure 2 – MFMET I glass Transfer standards chips (Design 01 to Design 07), manufactured by IMTAG

2.1.2 Microfluidic plastic chips

The so-called MFMET I polymer transfer standard chips (short: MFMET I TOPAS), manufactured by microfluidic ChipShop. The microfluidic chip is made from TOPAS (Thermoplastic Olefin Polymer with Amorphous Structure). It has eight different channels with various channel geometries, i.e. channel heights between 5 μm and 100 μm , channel widths between 5 μm and 100 μm and two channel lengths of 20 mm and 40 mm (see **Figure 3**).

Figure 3 – MFMET I polymer transfer standard chips, manufactured by microfluidic ChipShop.

2.2 Commercially available microfluidic chips

2.2.1 Microfluidic ChipShop

Commercially available microfluidic chips were selected by the partners from the microfluidic ChipShop product catalogue (<https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com/>) and kindly provided by microfluidic ChipShop as an in-kind contribution to the project.

Figure 4 – Commercially available microfluidic chips by microfluidic ChipShop.

Details regarding the microfluidic chips can be found in the catalogue by entering the respective item number (highlighted in yellow in **Figure 4**). All three microfluidic chips (Fluidic 145, Fluidic 144, Fluidic 156) shown have the same channel length (58.5 mm) but different channel heights and widths. Each microfluidic chip has four identical channels.

2.3 Microfluidic chips developed as part of MFMET II

Similar to the activities in the MFMET I project, this project also involves the manufacture of special microfluidic chips according to the specific needs of the project partners. This time, however, this only applies to microfluidic glass chips, which will be manufactured by IMTAG, the same manufacturer of the microfluidic glass chips used in the MFMET I project. For cost reasons, custom-made microfluidic plastic chips will not be produced in this project. Instead, it was decided to acquire commercially available microfluidic plastic chips that meet the requirements of the project partners.

2.3.1 Glass chips by IMTAG

Design1: channel height: 50 μm , channel width: 500 μm , channel lengths: 40 mm (straight), 70 mm (serpentine) and 40 mm (U-shape). The channel height of 50 μm was explicitly chosen in order to enable micro-PIV measurements to be carried out.

Design2: channel heights: 75 μm (CH1), 50 μm (CH2), 25 μm (CH3) and 25 μm (CH4); channel widths: 1000 μm (CH1), 400 μm (CH2), 400 μm (CH3) and 80 μm (CH4), all channel lengths: 40 mm.

Design4: channel heights of both big chambers: 75 μm , channel height of the small chamber: 50 μm , the width of all access channels is 500 μm . The dimensions of the large chambers are 30.4 mm by 2.2 mm and those of the small chamber are 12.5 mm by 1.6 mm.

Figure 5 – Design 1, Same channel dimensions but different channel architectures.

Figure 6 – Design 2: Four straight channels with the same channel length but different heights and widths.

Figure 7 – Design 4: A microfluidic chip specially designed for particle-laden flow (e.g. mixed depths).

2.3.2 Other microfluidic chips

To provide a greater selection of materials, project partner INESC MN and project collaborator TNO will manufacture additional microfluidic chips and make them available to project partners. The planned chips are based on the layout of the IMTAG microfluidic chip Design 2. INESC MN will be responsible to produce silicon/silicon microfluidic chips, whereas TNO will produce LCD microfluidic chips. It is asserted that the INESC MN microfluidic chips will have identical dimensions to the IMTAG microfluidic chip, and that the TNO microfluidic chips will have dimensions corresponding to those of the IMTAG microfluidic chips, as far as manufacturing technology allows.

3 Test liquids

The primary focus of the work is on Newtonian fluids. Because Newtonian fluids have shear-independent viscosity, this greatly simplifies the modelling and prediction of flow and pressure drop behaviour.

3.1 Ultra-pure degassed water

Water and simple aqueous salt solutions such as Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS) or sodium chloride (NaCl) are considered Newtonian fluids in microfluidics, as the viscosity of these fluids remains independent of the shear rate. Water is often used as the preferred test medium in microfluidics because its physical properties, such as viscosity, density and surface tension, are well characterised and international standardised. In addition, water is inexpensive, readily available, and easy to obtain in high purity, making it particularly suitable for repeatable measurement series and the validation of microfluidic systems and devices. Owing to its chemical neutrality regarding common chip materials, such as glass, silicon, or thermoplastic polymers, water rarely causes undesirable material interactions. As a non-toxic and easy-to-handle medium, it also allows for experiments without additional safety requirements. Since many biological fluids have aqueous properties, water provides a practical basis for investigating microfluidic processes under quasi-biological conditions.

3.2 Simulated Body Fluid (SBF)

SBF is a standardised laboratory solution that mimics the chemical conditions of human blood plasma. It is a Newtonian liquid which enables reproducible testing of materials and components that are later to be used in the human body. This includes the use of microfluidic devices.

3.3 Calibration oils

Calibration oils serve as Certified Reference Materials (CRM) to ensure the measurement accuracy of viscometers and density meters. Unlike commercial oils, they possess precisely defined physical properties that are traceable to international primary standards. The reliability of these oils is guaranteed through metrological traceability. This implies that every measurement is linked to an unbroken chain of comparisons back to a national metrology institute (NMI). Due to their chemical stability and documented technical data, calibration oils ensure reproducible results and fulfil the strict requirements of international quality management systems. The plan is to use two calibration oils with the same density at 20 °C but with two different but defined dynamic viscosities (e.g. 25 mPa·s and 80 mPa·s).

4 Temperatures

Temperature is a key parameter in microfluidic measurements, as both the fluid properties and behaviour of the microchannel structures (materials) are dependent on temperature. In this study, two elevated temperatures, in particular, a temperature close to 37 °C and 50 °C, were selected as representative operating conditions to cover typical applications and potential more extreme conditions.

A temperature of about 37 °C is close to physiological body temperature and is therefore particularly relevant for microfluidic systems that work with biological samples (e.g. blood, cell cultures or particle-containing suspensions). In this range, fluids often exhibit altered rheological properties, in particular, reduced viscosity compared to ambient temperature conditions. This directly influences the pressure drop and flow resistance in microchannels. In addition, particle and cell interaction behaviour can vary depending on temperature, which must be considered when designing and evaluating measurement methods for pressure drop and particle-laden flow transport.

The temperature range around 50 °C is close to an elevated temperature scenario that could occur in microfluidic reactor platforms, polymer processing, and thermal stability testing. At these temperatures, the viscosity of many fluids decreases significantly, resulting in lower flow resistance and altered pressure drops. In addition, many microfluidic materials, especially polymers such as PDMS, are sensitive to elevated temperatures. Effects such as thermal expansion, changes in elasticity, and altered wetting and surface properties can measurably influence the hydraulic properties (flow resistance) of a microfluidic chip. In addition, the risk of gas bubble formation (outgassing) increases, which can lead to inaccuracies in flow measurements.

5 Simulation tools

Simulations are used to complement and support the experimental characterisation of pressure drop and flow resistance in microfluidic systems and devices. The software helps validate measurement results, reduce uncertainty, and identify potential issues prior to practical implementation. It facilitates the model-based analysis of Newtonian fluids under various temperature conditions, providing a valuable foundation for selecting appropriate testing and evaluation methods. The software calculates the laminar flow behaviour, enabling the pressure drop, velocity fields, and flow profiles to be accurately predicted for different microchannel geometries.

Simulations are also used to investigate the effects of temperature-dependent parameter changes on the hydraulic properties of microchannels. Changes in the viscosity of the test medium and potential material-related effects can be considered. Furthermore, simulations offer opportunities for exploratory simulations of particle-laden flows, which are often difficult to capture experimentally. This includes, for example, particle (cell) transport, sedimentation, or potential deposition and clogging processes in microfluidic structures.

5.1 COMSOL

COMSOL Multiphysics is a commercial finite element method (FEM) simulation platform that can be used to model, calculate, and visualise various physical phenomena. COMSOL also can model particle-laden flows using the CFD interface and dedicated particle-tracking tools.

5.2 CFD (OpenFOAM)

OpenFOAM (Open Source Field Operation And Manipulation) is an open-source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) toolbox. Similar to COMSOL, it provides several approaches to simulate particle-laden flows, ranging from dilute suspensions to dense multiphase systems. It offers high flexibility because different solvers and libraries can be combined depending on particle concentration, physics, and required accuracy.

5.3 ANSYS Fluent

ANSYS Fluent is used to simulate single- and multi-phase flows, heat transfer and complex transport problems. Steady-state and transient flow problems are solved using the finite volume discretisation method and a variety of physical models suitable for different flow regimes. Depending on the complexity of the geometry, calculation meshes are generated using structured, unstructured or hybrid methods. Simulations are performed using dedicated computing resources with parallel processing, which enables parametric studies and time-dependent simulations to be carried out with sufficient spatial and temporal resolution.

6 Experiments and simulations

The objective of this study is to develop methods for characterising pressure drop and flow resistance for different fluids and temperatures for at least two microfluidic devices. The methods will be tested using microfluidic transfer, standard microfluidic chips, or commercially available microfluidic chips.

These methods will ensure metrological traceability and comparability for various flows relevant to microfluidics and will include proposals for uncertainty estimation.

6.1 Experiments focused on pressure drop and flow resistance for a **particle-free** liquid. The experiments should cover different temperatures and liquids (A1.2.3).

RISE, LEI, IPQ, UofG, DTI, FOG, CETIAT

Partner	Method(s)	Microfluidic devices under test	Flow rate range [µl/min]	Pressure range [mbar]	Liquids and Temperatures [° C]	Comments
RISE	High-precision syringe pump & pressure sensors	<u>Plastic:</u> 10000087 10000089	0 to 1000	0 to 5000	Water SBF	For most experiments, the same conditions should be used for both methods.
	Pressure-driven flow controller	<u>Glass:</u> Design2 ch4 [opt: Design2 ch2 and/or ch3]	0 to 7	0 to 2000	Ambient temperature (22 °C ± 0.5 °C)	
LEI	High-precision syringe pump	<u>Plastic:</u> 10000087 10000089	23.9 nL/min to 100 ml/min	0 to 8000	Water SBF	

	Pressure-driven flow controller	10000091 Glass:			Newtonian or non-Newtonian fluids, at room temperature (22 ± 5°C)	
IPQ	Pressure controller	Plastic: 10000087 10000089 10000091	0 to 1000	0 to 2000	Water SBF Oil	Ambient temperature
	Syringe pump & pressure sensors	Glass: Design2 ch1 Design2 ch2 Design2 ch3 Design2 ch4	0 to 1000	0 to 5000		
UofG	High-precision syringe pump Pressure-driven flow controller	Plastic: 10000087 10000089 10000091 Glass: Design2 ch2 Design4 ch4	0 to 1000	0 to 2000	Water SBF Ambient temperature (20 °C)	
DTI	Pressure controller Syringe pump	Plastic: 10000087 10000089 10000091 Glass: Design2 ch1 Design2 ch2 Design2 ch3 Design2 ch4	0.1 to 1000	10 to 4000	Water 20 °C, 37 °C, 50 °C SBF	
CETIAT (with FOG support)	Pressure controller	Plastic: 10000087 10000089 10000091 Glass: Design2 ch1 Design2 ch2 Design2 ch3 Design2 ch4	0 to 400 (same range as MFMET 1 results)	0 to 200 (same range as MFMET 1 results)	Water 20 ; (30) ; 37 ; (50) °C SBF Oil	Wider ranges depending on pressure drop of the chips ranges indicated are the maximum allowed by channel 1 of the pressure controller, wider range is achievable with channel 2 (to be verified) and use of syringe-pump flow measurement: optic method for 20 °C ; Bronkhorst ML120 for other temperatures (in climatic chamber)

6.2 CFD simulations focused on pressure drop and flow resistance for a **particle-free liquid**. The simulations should cover different temperatures and liquids (A1.2.4).

CMI, INESC MN, LEI

Partner	Software	Microfluidic devices as example	Flow rate range [µl/min]	Pressure range [mbar]	Liquids and Temperatures [° C]	Comments
CMI	OpenFOAM	Any design microfluidic channel	0 to 1000	Any pressure	Any liquid with known physical parameters	

INESC MN	COMSOL	Any design microfluidic channel	0 to 1000	Any pressure	Any liquid with known physical parameters	
LEI	ANSYS Fluent	Any design microfluidic channel	0 to 1000	Any pressure	Any liquid with known physical parameters and, $T > 0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	

6.3 Exploratory study of methods (experiments and simulations) on the possibility of determining pressure drop and flow resistance for **particle-laden** flows (A1.2.5).

INESC MN, FOG, UofG, DTI, CMI

Simulations:

Partner	Experiment / Software	Microfluidic devices as example	Flow rate range* [$\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$]	Pressure range* [mbar]	Liquids and Temperatures [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Comments
CMI	OpenFOAM	Any design microfluidic channel	0 to 1000	Any pressure	Any liquid with known physical parameters e.g. water, oil	
INESC MN	COMSOL [CFD Module (for fluid flow) with the Particle Tracing Module (for tracking particles)]	Any design microfluidic channel	0 to 1000	Any pressure	Any liquid with known physical parameters	

* There are no limits

INESC MN will use two approaches:

* one-way coupling (low particle concentration) by calculating the fluid velocity and pressure (Laminar Flow interface) first, then compute the particle trajectories using the calculated fluid field.

* two-way coupling (high particle loading) considering particles affect the flow. Flow and particles will be simulated simultaneously in a time-dependent study, enabling forces like drag, gravity, and pressure gradient to act on particles, which then exert a reverse force on the fluid.

Experiments:

Partner	Method(s)	Microfluidic devices under test	Flow rate range [$\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$]	Pressure range [mbar]	Liquids and Temperatures [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Comments (kind of particles etc.)
UofG	Syring Pump	Design2 Ch1 or design 2 ch2	0.1 to 1000	10 to 4000	Room temperature	Fluorescence beads. We will monitor the concentration of beads since it may affect the measurement.

DTI	Syringe pump	Design2 ch1 or Design2 ch2	0.1 to 1000	10 to 4000	Room temperature	
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DTI suggestion of a particle-laden flow experiment regarding flow resistance:

A cleaning procedure for removing particles from the system may involve alternating cycles of flushing with demineralised water, mild detergent solution, or isopropanol. The cleaning procedure must be reliable enough to prevent risks of particle contamination to other interests in the microflow laboratory.

A syringe pump is calibrated for volumetric flow. Polystyrene beads of small size, e.g. 1 μm , are suspended in demineralised water, and the suspension is homogenised by shaking or stirring. Using Stokes law of settling the assumption of a homogenous suspension is verified, by comparing that the settling time of the particles in the system are orders of magnitude larger than the duration of the experiment.

The syringe pump generates a flow that is conducted through the channel of a microfluidic chip and a pressure sensor. Matching series of flow setpoint and pressure are measured, for each value of particle concentration while varying the particle concentration. Ideally, the particle concentration should start from values like μPIV and be increased until the particles start to affect the pressure drop and hydrodynamic resistance. Figure 8 shows a proposed experimental setup for such an experiment at the DTI microflow laboratory.

A)

B)

Figure 8 – Proposed experimental setup for determining pressure drop and hydrodynamic resistance at the DTI microflow laboratory. P is a pressure sensor. A) Measurement of pressure drop from system to atmosphere. B) Measurement of pressure drop from system + microfluidic device to atmosphere.

If a cheap particle counter is available, it may be added to the setup in **Figure 8** to verify that the particle concentration remains constant throughout the experiment. A risk in the proposed experiment is that the pressure sensor and microfluidic device may become dysfunctional because of particle contamination. Solutions of polystyrene beads should be disposed of as chemical waste.

The channel used could be IMTAG glass chip Design2, ch2. The temperature is room temperature, and the liquid is demineralised water. The particles could be polystyrene beads, and their size and concentration could match the smaller beads used in A1.1.3.

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